

The current report presents the scalability of BioExcel CoE's flagship codes: GROMACS, HADDOCK, CP2K, and workflow solutions with PyCOMPSs, BioBB and PMX.

GROMACS

Report on Application Scalability progress

Name of the code	GROMACS
URL	manual.gromacs.org
Application Domain	Life sciences, material sciences
Supported Key Methods (if applicable) ¹	Molecular dynamics
License	LGPL v2 or higher

In life sciences, which is the target area of BioExcel, the size of the molecular systems of interest are largely fixed and thus target to strong scaling only. However, the action of molecules in organisms always occurs through ensembles of molecules. Modern sampling techniques also make use of ensemble techniques from physics to provide both scaling and often super-linear acceleration. The scalability goals are thus improving strong scaling for individual (solvated) molecules combined with improving weak scaling using ensemble techniques. Together these provide the path to exascale.

Speed Up Achievements

The main focus up till now has been on improving strong scaling on combined CPU-GPU systems, which will be the dominating type of exascale systems. For the combined weak scaling we have been working on several ensemble techniques, of which the accelerated weight histogram method is a main one.

¹ Many simulation codes support a range of different methods and can be seen as a collection of codes and in particular scalability depends significantly on the method selected.

Figure 1: Combined simulation and ensemble scaling of aquaporin

In Figure 1 we show a showcase scaling test of a permeation study of aquaporin. The original scientific study was published without this scaling at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-21357-2>. This computation involves computing a free-energy profile of permeation of water or ammonia through four different mutants of aquaporin. During the first BioExcel project we developed the ensemble parallelization for AWH and ported more computation to GPUs. Here multiple walkers, each consisting of a copy of the system, share sampling information every second to improve the biasing potential. During BioExcel2 we implemented direct communication between GPUs in a co-design effort with Nvidia, which enables the use of up to 4 V100 GPUs for a single, relatively small system of 110000 atoms. Combined these improvements enable a reduction of time to solution of a factor 32 when using the whole of Puthi at CSC in Finland, comprising 5120 Intel Cascade Lake cores at 2.1 GHz and 512 Nvidia V100 GPUs.

The PMX free-energy package uses GROMACS as the simulation engine and therefore we report the scaling of PMX in this document. PMX leverages strong scaling improvements of GROMACS. In addition, it provides significant ensemble type scaling by performing many short non-equilibrium simulations starting from equilibrated conformations.

Figure 2: Scaling of the Merck dataset to the whole of Raven.

As a demonstration of the power of PMX, we computed binding free energies for the whole dataset <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.0c00900> provided by the pharmaceutical company Merck. The whole of Raven, 48000 Intel Cascade Lake cores, was used for this which resulted in a time to solution of 3 days and linear scaling from 1 node. With one node this calculation would take 4.1 years. It is difficult to provide a baseline here, as PMX joined the BioExcel centre at the start of BioExcel2 and provides new, integrated methods to nearly fully automated do such large calculation, which were not possible before.

In Figure 3. we also show a strong scaling benchmark of a large molecular system.

All molecular dynamics codes that compete with GROMACS come from the US: NAMD, Amber and CHARMM. Of these GROMACS is by far the most popular code not only in the EU, but world-wide, likely due to its combination of good performance, usability and open source license.

Hardware and Performance portability

GROMACS currently has co-design efforts with all major CPU and GPU vendors: Nvidia, Intel, AMD and Fujitsu. In the past we have done prototyping work on FPGAs where GROMACS worked well, but was not price competitive with GPUs, which will also seem to be present in nearly all exa-scale machines. GROMACS uses state-of-the-art algorithms which are tailor-made for both SIMD and GPU architectures. Often the same algorithm works very well on both SIMD and GPUs but is quite different from the standard algorithms in the community. All compute intensive kernels have been ported to CUDA for running on Nvidia GPUs and the most important ones to OpenCL for other architectures. Porting the kernels takes some effort but is often unproblematic. It is mostly the setup and communication code that takes the most time and is most bug prone. Here co-design efforts have helped to reduce the efforts of the GROMACS team, but also especially to let us focus on the common, more algorithmic aspects while vendors focus on the vendor specific aspects. Currently there are co-design efforts underway to port GROMACS to SYCL and HIP targeting AMD and Intel GPUs.

Correctness of GPU code is tested by running the standard GROMACS unit and integration tests which are agnostic to the (CPU or GPU) back-end.

Roadmap summary

During 2021 and 2022:

- Porting of main GROMACS compute kernels and data management code to SYCL and HIP. This is a co-design effort with Intel and AMD.
- Improve scaling of the 3D FFTs on GPUs in the particle-mesh Ewald electrostatics method. This is a co-design effort with Nvidia.
- Improved integration of ensemble methods in GROMACS

GROMACS can already make good use of pre-exascale machines with Nvidia GPUs. Work is ongoing for porting to AMD GPUs. There are two issues here. Currently it is unfortunately still unknown what the best programming model is to target AMD GPUs and it is difficult to get access to AMD GPUs for testing.

Our scalability roadmap is to keep increasing the strong scaling of individual systems as the ensemble scaling. It is not possible to provide hard numbers for these, as GROMACS is highly optimised and already makes very good use of the hardware, thus performance improvements depend to a large extent on communication latencies and improvements in ensemble algorithms which are difficult to foresee. However, it is clear that both these will improve over the coming years and GROMACS will leverage these.

References

[GROMACS: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers](#)

MJ Abraham, T Murtola, R Schulz, S Páll, JC Smith, B Hess, E Lindahl
SoftwareX 1, 19-25

[GROMACS 4.5: a high-throughput and highly parallel open source molecular simulation toolkit](#)

S Pronk, S Páll, R Schulz, P Larsson, P Bjelkmar, R Apostolov, MR Shirts, ...
Bioinformatics 29 (7), 845-854

Experiment

What does an exascale application and data set look like? What requirement does this impose on the system:

1. Can you reasonably partition your application across a system of this size?
Given a problem which provides sufficient ensemble parallelism, yes.
2. Does each node have a large enough parcel of work to do?

Molecular systems are rather small, so each node will often run a single copy of the system, in particular if one node contains many GPUs, as is expected at exascale. Ensemble parallelism will provide parallelism between (many) nodes.

3. What sort underlying memory hierarchy is required to support efficient computation at scale?
 - **Memory is not of interest for GROMACS, as all important data for the major computations fits in cache.**
4. What interconnect is required?
 - **Low latency and interference is by far the most important for GROMACS**
5. Where are the bottlenecks – how will you overcome them?
6. Should the system be homogeneous or heterogeneous?
Ideally CPUs+GPUs, the ratio is flexible as we can move computation between them.
7. Should the system be flat or have different local areas for different parts of the application?
Flat.
8. How does the application (or system) manage resilience?
 - **GROMACS checkpoints, by default every 15 minutes. This has very little overhead.**

9. What about the numerical stability of the algorithms at exascale?

There are no particular issues with stability at exascale. If there are stability issues, if there are present at small scale already.

Also, what is your target in terms of exascale capacity needs (use case, grand challenge) and when (2025, 2030, 2040)?

There are very many unsolved, important problems in molecular life sciences which could fill an exascale machine at any time.

HADDOCK

Report on Application Scalability progress

Name of the code	HADDOCK
URL	https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock2.4 https://github.com/haddock/haddock3
Application Domain	Life sciences, modelling of biomolecular complexes (e.g. including COVID19 complexes), drug screening
Supported Key Methods (if applicable) ²	Docking based on energy minimisation and molecular dynamics
License	Apache-2.0

HADDOCK [1,2] is an integrative modelling software that allows researchers to model complexes between biomolecules. One of the BioExcel use cases aims at modelling the complete network of interactions in a given organism. The size of the problem is defined by the number of constituents in the network to the square. **Our scalability goals are therefore to deliver in the shortest time possible models of all to be predicted interactions, which is a strong scaling problem.** By increasing the number of nodes on which the computations are distributed we can reduce the time to solution.

Speed Up Achievements

HADDOCK main use is in HTC mode. The submissions via HADDOCK web portal for example make heavy use of EOSC HTC resources. In the context of BioExcel we have developed a MPI-based HADDOCK resource manager that distributes the workload on all allocated nodes in an HPC system. First benchmarking results indicate a strong scaling, linear with the number of nodes allocated (Figure 1 and Table 1).

² Many simulation codes support a range of different methods and can be seen as a collection of codes and in particular scalability depends significantly on the method selected.

Figure 1: HADDOCK scaling performance.

Table 1: HADDOCK Scaling performance

Nodes	Core	Timing [min]	Speedup
1	96	1050	1,0
2	192	529	2,0
5	480	193	5,4
10	960	100	10,5
50	4800	20	52,5

The reported benchmark task consists of modelling 100 biomolecular complexes of similar size (which defines the computational requirements per complex), running the full HADDOCK workflow consisting of the sampling of 10'000 models per complex and refinement of the best 200, based on a combination of short molecular dynamics and energy minimization as implemented in HADDOCK (see <https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock2.4/protocol/> for details). Complexes are taken from the Docking Benchmark 5, available from <https://github.com/haddock/BM5-clean>. The computations are performed for each complex using a full node (96 threads) and writing to the local file system (~800MB of data). The compressed result archive (~50MB) is transferred to the master node upon completion.

There are various other docking and integrative modelling software being developed around the world such as the Integrative Modelling Platform (IMP) [3], ZDOCK [4], CLUSPRO [5], LightDock [6] and ATTRACT [7] to cite a few, with the last two being the only other EU code in this list. Each software has however its own features and application purpose. HADDOCK is the most versatile in terms of type of problems addressed, from small molecule docking to large macromolecular assemblies. It is also one of the few software that allows the modelling of more than two molecules simultaneously. As far as we are aware no scaling benchmarks have been reported for any of those codes.

Hardware and Performance portability

HADDOCK is composed of a Python (with support for legacy 2.x and current 3.x series) and scripts executed by the CNS (Crystallography and NMR System) software (Fortran 77) (<http://cns-online.org/v1.3>). Both Python and CNS software have been running as part of the HADDOCK project natively in x86 and x86-64 architectures for years. Recently, the HADDOCK software has been compiled and tested successfully on ARMv7l architecture (Raspberry Pi 4 model B, 2GB and 4GB of physical memory). Due to its few software library dependencies (only standard C and Fortran language libraries) and its small memory footprint, its execution on the Raspberry Pi platform was not an issue, despite the physical memory-limit of the hardware.

Thanks to its simple and standard dependencies and its small footprint, we expect that HADDOCK could be also supported on FPGA hardware without major problems. About near future platforms such as the EuroHPC system prototypes or the European processor, prototyped hardware has been developed and presented by the Mont-Blanc project (<https://www.montblanc-project.eu/>). This project has developed several ARM-based prototypes, with a similar architecture compared to the Raspberry Pi project. Thus, we would expect our software to run on the projected architectures without major issues on hardware and software restraints.

Roadmap summary

Within BioExcel we have developed a prototype MPI-based HADDOCK manager that allowed us to demonstrate strong scaling on a still rather limited number of nodes/cores. In the coming period our CoE should get access to pre-exascale machines on which we will further benchmark HADDOCK, on both larger numbers of complexes to model (i.e. increased size of the problem), and more heterogeneous datasets that will bring the challenge of properly orchestrating the computations to avoid load imbalance between nodes.

Because of the size of the problem, the best route to shortening the time to solution lies rather in efficient distribution and management of the computations on a large number of nodes rather than speeding up the computation of a single model. For this reason we do not intend to port the existing code to GPGPUs. Instead we might replace (in a longer future) part of the workflow to make use of Gromacs which can very efficiently harvest GPGPUs.

Note that within BioExcel we have an alternative route toward exascale by making use of the PyCOMPSs framework developed by the BSC partner within BioExcel. A PyCOMPSs-HADDOCK workflow was successfully demonstrated at MareNotrum BSC.

Another challenge will be the handling of the huge amount of data generated by such computations. While during the computations the data remain on a node, the results (compressed archives of a few 100MBs) have to be transferred and stored on the master node. A full modelling of the human interactome might generate 10 Exabytes of compressed data. The post-processing and analysis of those does cause data analytics and I/O challenges. To this end, in BioExcel we have developed a benchmark to evaluate the timing and I/O bottlenecks of processing 1'000'000 files ([10.5281/zenodo.3271424](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3271424)).

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Experiment

What does an exascale application and data set look like? What requirement does this impose on the system:

1. Can you reasonably partition your application across a system of this size?

Yes

2. Does each node have a large enough parcel of work to do?

Yes

3. What sort of underlying memory hierarchy is required to support efficient computation at scale?
 - size of memory per node and speed

At least 4GB of memory per core

4. What interconnect is required?

- speed and topology

Communication/data transfer to/from a node only occurs at the start and end of a workload unit. As such rather standard interconnects will do.

5. Where are the bottlenecks – how will you overcome them?

For very large sets of complexes to be modelled, the amount of generated data will reach Exabytes and the number of files on the system millions to billions (if unpacked). This will bring data analytics and I/O challenges for the post-processing, but not for the data generation (computing) part.

6. Should the system be homogeneous or heterogeneous?

For HADDOCK, a homogeneous system would be best, but in principle the machinery should be able to handle heterogeneous systems.

7. Should the system be flat or have different local areas for different parts of the application?

Flat

8. How does the application (or system) manage resilience?
 - checkpoint: how often, how big, impact on performance?

Internal checks with high fault tolerance. Catching and relaunching of failed models within one workload task

9. What about the numerical stability of the algorithms at exascale?

No special issues foreseen at this time.

Also, what is your target in terms of exascale capacity needs (use case, grand challenge) and when (2025, 2030, 2040)?

We foresee two use cases / grand challenges.

- 1) **Faster drug repurposing for emerging virus (fast pandemic response) (expected 2025)**

In the current COVID19 pandemic HADDOCK was used to screen ~2000 approved drugs against four targets (proteins). This screening was performed using the EOSC HTC resources and took more than one month.

- <https://www.bonvinlab.org/covid/>
- <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/news/haddock-support-covid-19-research>
- <https://instruct-eric.eu/haddock-screen-of-2000-approved-drugs-for-covid19>
- <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/european-digital-infrastructures-support-coronavirus-research>

- <https://www.egi.eu/use-cases/research-stories/haddock-helps-scientists-to-advance-covid-19-research>

As an exascale use case, for a newly emerging virus, the aim would be to run the drug repurposing screen of a larger number of compounds (e.g. 5000) against a few targets (e.g. 5), which all together might amount to around 25000 docking runs. On an exascale system, using for example 5000 nodes, this entire screening should complete within half an hour to one hour.

2) Interactome modelling (targets for 2030 and 2040)

This use case is about adding the structural dimension to interactomes, which represent the network of connections between proteins in an organism at the origin of all molecular functions and communication. Disruption of those interactions or miscommunication is at the origin of many diseases which why adding the structural dimension by modelling the underlying complexes is important as it will open the route to rational, structure-based therapeutic intervention. And when the network wiring is unknown, a related challenge is to predict it by modelling all possible pairs of interactions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Illustration of the interactome exascale challenge

The size of the associated challenges will depend on the complexity of the considered organism. For bacteria, the genome encodes for about 6000 proteins while for human around 20'000. Predicting the interactome would thus require in the order of $6'000^2/2$ to $20'000^2/2$ docking runs (18 millions or 200 millions), each generating hundreds of MBs of data. As we have 3D structures of only $\frac{2}{3}$ to half of the proteins, the size of the problem reduces but remains a huge challenge. Using 10000 nodes of an exascale system, this interactome 3D prediction would still require between one week to one month to complete (possible target for 2040).

A more realistic scenario would be to add the structural dimension to the known interactome, which, in the case of human, is estimated to consist of several hundred thousands of complexes. Assuming having access by 2030 to 2500 nodes for a workload of 100'000 units

(complexes), HADDOCK should be able to model those in approximately 10 hours (target 2030).

CP2K

Report on Application Scalability progress

Name of the code	GROMACS + CP2K
URL	https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k https://gitlab.com/aracsmd/gromacs/
Application Domain	Quantum chemistry in biomolecular simulation
Supported Key Methods (if applicable) ³	hybrid quantum/classical (QM/MM) molecular dynamics, DFT
License	CP2K: GPL GROMACS: LGPL

With regards to GROMACS and CP2K, the goals of BioExcel are:

1. Provide an interface within GROMACS that couples the two codes to perform QM/MM simulation, thereby making CP2K's quantum chemistry and QM-MM coupling capabilities available to the biomolecular user community through GROMACS. We refer to this coupled usage as GROMACS+CP2K.
2. Ensure CP2K's existing QM/MM parallel scaling capabilities are efficiently utilised through interfaced execution from GROMACS.
3. Improve CP2K's QM/MM parallel scaling, specifically for problem sizes and QM treatments/parametrisations relevant for biomolecular simulation

These goals encompass mostly strong scaling for fixed problem size, typically corresponding to a biomolecular region of interest of fixed spatial extent / number of atoms treated quantum mechanically.

Speed Up Achievements

For CP2K, our hybrid MPI+OpenMP optimisations of QM/MM subroutines - incorporated into the official CP2K 8.1 release - have improved performance for constant problem size for biomolecular benchmarks by enabling effective usage of more than one thread per MPI rank, achieving for example for the benchmark system shown in Figure 1 roughly a factor 2.5 improvement in scaling relative to performance at project start with a single thread per MPI rank.

³ Many simulation codes support a range of different methods and can be seen as a collection of codes and in particular scalability depends significantly on the method selected.

Figure 1: Improved strong scaling speedup of CP2K walltime per molecular dynamics step using QM/MM thanks to our addition of OpenMP threading optimisations, with best performance improvement obtained with 6 threads per MPI rank. Results are for CIC ion channel simulation, 253 QM atoms treated with a low level of QM theory (BLYP functional) and 150k classical (MM) atoms, executed on ARCHER (CRAY XC30) with full utilisation of 24 Intel Xeon (Ivy Bridge) cores per node, 64GB memory per node.

This benchmark is available at https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3885123>

As an example of the kind of parallel scaling we have made available to our user community through the newly developed interface enabling combined usage of GROMACS together with CP2K for QM/MM simulation we show in Figure 2 the speedup for constant problem size for a biomolecular benchmark of small-modest size (68 QM atoms) and high level of QM theory (MP2). Parallel efficiency close to 90% is obtained on 64 nodes (1536 Intel Xeon Ivy Bridge cores), and close to 70% on 128 nodes (3072 cores).

Figure 2: Strong parallel scaling speedup of CP2K walltime per molecular dynamics step using QM/MM available through the GROMACS-CP2K interface. Results are for CBD-PHY bacteriophytochrome simulation, 68 QM atoms treated with a high level of QM theory (MP2) and 170k classical (MM) atoms, executed on ARCHER (CRAY XC30) with full utilisation of 24 Intel Xeon (Ivy Bridge) cores per node, 64GB memory per node.

This benchmark is available at https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3885123>

We have implemented a powerful facility for performing efficient large-scale computations using the GROMACS Accelerated Weight histogram (AWH) sampling method coupled with CP2K. In the following example, shown on Figure 3, we have tested parallel scaling in the computation of the free energy profile for the isomerization reaction inside the CBD-PHY protein system for which results are also shown above. This is parallelized using several sampling “walkers” which together build up the profile, speeding-up profile computation almost linearly (i.e. 100% parallel efficiency). This solves a problem of fixed size (free energy profile determination for a given system) hence is an example of excellent strong scaling.

Figure 3: Strong parallel scaling of the AWH free-energy profile computation using GROMACS-CP2K interface. Speed-up relative to 1 node is shown on the left panel and has near perfect scaling. Total approximate time to solve the free-energy profile problem is shown on the right

panel. Results are for CBD-PHY bacteriophytochrome simulation, 68 QM atoms treated with a DFT method (PBE) and 170k classical (MM) atoms, executed on Mahti (Atos BullSequana XH2000) with full utilisation of 128 AMD Epyc (Rome) cores per node, 256GB memory per node.

Hardware and Performance portability

Performance portability to GPUs of GROMACS+CP2K depends on the portability and offloading efficiency of CP2K's QM/MM calculations as these are by far more computationally intense than GROMACS execution in these calculations.

With regards to EuroHPC systems containing Nvidia GPUs, CP2K directly incorporates CUDA. For the relatively small system sizes (i.e. QM regions of interest) relevant to our biomolecular use cases CUDA offloading has historically yielded variable and generally at most modest performance advantages on a per-node basis compared to running purely on available CPUs, though this depends on the type of QM treatment chosen and on EuroHPC systems will also depend on the relative performance of available CPUs and GPUs per node. The CP2K core developers, who are external to BioExcel, have in a recent (January 2021) major release introduced significant changes to core CUDA offloading functionality, which may yield greater benefit.

With regards to EuroHPC systems containing AMD GPUs, a smaller subset of CP2K execution than for Nvidia GPUs through CUDA can be offloaded indirectly thanks to support for HIP in the DBCSR library used by CP2K for sparse matrix multiplication. Given the relatively large sizes of systems for which functions in this library are used compared to sizes for biomolecular systems, this may yield only a modest performance boost compared to running on CPUs only.

Access for CoEs to a testbed system with a reasonable number of nodes equipped with AMD GPUs would aid preparation in support of our users of upcoming EuroHPC systems such as LUMI.

Roadmap summary

The status and roadmap of CP2K portability to Nvidia and AMD GPUs relevant to petascale and pre-exascale EuroHPC systems is as described above: CP2K has native CUDA offloading. HIP is not directly supported in the code, though some linear algebra operations (sparse matrix multiplications) that are less used for biomolecular applications based on QM system sizes can be offloaded to AMD GPUs through HIP support in the DBCSR library used by CP2K. GROMACS supports Nvidia GPUs through CUDA and AMD GPUs through OpenCL, and has new co-design projects targeting (improved) native acceleration through CUDA, SYCL and HIP covering all current major accelerator vendors (NVIDIA, AMD, Intel).

CP2K parallel scaling efficiency depends strongly on system size, i.e. for our purposes the number of atoms in a biomolecular system treated quantum mechanically and their spatial extent, which is small compared to traditional CP2K application domain usage, as well as on the type of QM treatment used, i.e. the quality of the approximation, for which there exist a wide variety of methods within the code. Efficient scaling varies accordingly from tens to thousands of cores depending on the user's chosen parameterization.

For execution purely on CPUs, current targets for additional performance and scaling improvements on top of those already delivered and reported above include load imbalance in QM/MM subroutines in constrained-memory contexts (specifically when selecting GRID instead of ATOM parallel decomposition scheme), serial execution of certain PW utility subroutines, and load balancing more broadly for CP2K's Quickstep module, for which we plan to determine optimal heuristics to improve balance and scaling specifically for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems.

For execution on CPUs+GPUs, core CP2K developers have recently developed a significantly modified CUDA-based offload scheme. We plan to work with CP2K developers by analysing performance and scaling for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems and providing feedback and suggestions on bottlenecks. We also plan to work with MaX CoE to incorporate performance on biomolecular benchmarks into training kernels for small matrix multiplication offloading through the DBCSR library wherever we perceive this to have potential impact on resulting performance and scaling.

Within GROMACS, we plan to implement efficient transition path methods, such as the nudged-elastic band (NEB) method. It allows simulation of the transition path for the reaction, splitting it into several optimizations. Thus usage of multiple points along the surface allows efficient parallel scaling of the whole problem and increases precision of the final reaction profile.

Regarding the GROMACS-CP2K interface, in order to pave the way for GROMACS+CP2K-based QM/MM simulations on exascale HPC resources that make efficient use of CP2K's parallel scaling performance, further development of the interface will consider in detail the design choices regarding parallel execution and in particular how the existing domain decomposition within GROMACS can be made to optimally make use of MPI-parallel execution of CP2K subroutines. MPI sub-communicators, which can be passed to relevant CP2K routines as an alternative to using all MPI ranks (MPI_COMM_WORLD), will be employed for flexible parallelism, where beneficial, such as to treat multiple QM regions.

We continue to prioritise and re-evaluate these above development targets on the basis of an ongoing systematic investigation of a QM/MM benchmark suite which we developed and continue to expand (see

https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite
and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3885123>).

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Experiment

Current trends:

- Fujitsu A64FX: 1 node = around 3 Tflop/s from 48 cores (single socket)
- AMD EPYC Rome 7742: 1 node = around 6 Tflop/s from 128 cores (2 x 64)

Exascale system: suppose around 10 Tflop/s (double precision) from 256 CPU cores per node, so exascale system contains 10^5 nodes. Total parallelism is $2.56 \cdot 10^7$.

Exascale system:

Supposing $O(10)$ Tflop/s (double precision) per node provided by $O(10^2)$ CPU cores, an exascale system would require $O(10^5)$ nodes. Considering CPU+GPU nodes suggests at most one order of magnitude fewer nodes in the case of several GPUs per node. Total parallelism on CPU-only assumption is $O(10^7)$.

What does an exascale application and data set look like?

For QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems the combined usage of GROMACS+CP2K that we have developed is a powerful tool for computing free energy profiles using the AWH method, for which results are shown above, as well as for computing transition paths and states using the NEB method. No significantly large input datasets are required nor generated using either method.

What requirement does this impose on the system:

1. *Can you reasonably partition your application across a system of this size?*

AWH-based free energy profile calculations in particular are amenable to being run efficiently on a sizeable fraction of an exascale machine with good parallel efficiency. NEB-based transition path calculations will be more sensitive to inhomogeneity in the biomolecular problem when run at very large parallel scale, so more work may be required to ensure balanced execution and efficient machine utilisation at scale.

2. *Does each node have a large enough parcel of work to do?*

Yes

3. *What sort underlying memory hierarchy is required to support efficient computation at scale?*
 - *size of memory per node and speed*

It would be desirable for future systems to provide no less than 2GB of primary fast main memory per CP2K MPI rank, in part because more memory per rank allows CP2K to store and fetch computed intermediate integrals rather than recomputing these periodically on the fly. Whilst hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution enables CP2K to reduce memory usage per rank, flexibility to run in pure MPI-parallel mode is important as MPI-only performance frequently exceeds hybrid performance. Hence at least 2GB of main on-node memory should ideally be provided per CPU core.

4. *What interconnect is required?*

- *speed and topology*

Interconnect performance characteristics resulting from network hardware, topology, traffic handling and tuned MPI library implementation are critical for obtaining good CP2K performance at scale as this can help reduce the cost of communication overheads, which we have observed to be a CP2K scaling bottleneck.

5. *Where are the bottlenecks – how will you overcome them?*

The AWH and NEB-based approaches outlined above enable excellent scaling and provide a powerful tool. Other types of CP2K simulations, especially with small system sizes and/or low-quality QM treatments are limited in scaling by communication overheads and other bottlenecks. Some of these bottlenecks are fundamental to the underlying algorithms employed and/or to their implementation in the core of CP2K and thus would require large-scale reworking by the core developers and possibly the implementation of new algorithms, whilst others such as those we have outlined as development targets in the Roadmap Summary above can be tackled more directly.

6. *Should the system be homogeneous or heterogeneous?*

Ongoing developments in accelerator support in CP2K may widen the space of simulation types and parameters for which GPU offloading yields a performance advantage, however as GPU availability is not a critical performance criterion for CP2K the question of whether the system should have one homogeneous architecture or be partitioned should be dictated more by overall system usage, i.e. requirements from all applications being run on the system, as well as by economic/financial, power supply infrastructure and environmental considerations.

7. *Should the system be flat or have different local areas for different parts of the application?*

The GROMACS+CP2K implementation does not have a clear demand for concurrent cross-architecture execution.

8. *How does the application (or system) manage resilience?*

- *checkpoint: how often, how big, impact on performance?*

Both GROMACS and CP2K have some form of checkpoint/restart functionality that can be employed, which should be possible to integrate with the GROMACS interface code to enable GROMACS to effectively restart CP2K calculation.

9. *What about the numerical stability of the algorithms at exascale?*

No major issues are foreseen at the time. Numerical stability for the AWH and NEB-based approach described above should be the same as for smaller-scale CP2K simulations.

Also, what is your target in terms of exascale capacity needs (use case, grand challenge) and when (2025, 2030, 2040)?

The improved scaling of CP2K used in conjunction with GROMACS described above will make it possible to address the grand challenge of sampling the parts of the free energy surface relevant for a quantitative understanding of enzyme catalytic effects on exascale computing facilities by 2025.

PyMDSetup (WF)

Report on Application Scalability progress

Name of the code	PyMDSetup
URL	https://github.com/bioexcel/pymdsetup
Application Domain	Molecular Dynamics simulations
Supported Key Methods (if applicable) ⁴	
License	Apache 2

PyMDSetup is an automated protocol to model residue mutations in 3D protein structures detected from genomics data, and prepare and run Molecular Dynamics simulations for all the generated structures. The pipeline receives a wild type protein structure file (in PDB format) and a set of mutations as input. Next, it prepares and runs MD simulations for each of the systems, thus obtaining static information (an ensemble of modelled structures for each of the protein variants), and dynamic data (trajectories for each of the protein variants). Both types of information can later be used in a comparative study. All the MD steps are run using the GROMACS MD package and the PyCOMPSs programming framework is used to define the tasks of the workflow and to parallelize the execution.

⁴ Many simulation codes support a range of different methods and can be seen as a collection of codes and in particular scalability depends significantly on the method selected.

Fig. 1.- PyMDSetup flowchart

The test case chosen to run a massively parallel execution using the described workflow is the Pyruvate Kinase protein (PDB code 2VGB). To be able to get the most out of the combination of PyCOMPSs and the PyMDSetup workflow, a set of 200 mutations consisting on reported pathogenic variants were manually selected from the whole set of variants available at the UniprotKB database⁵, and used as input. With these inputs, the generated workflow can sequentially run 200 totally independent MD simulations, which are then parallelized by PyCOMPSs.

The experiments focus on evaluating the scalability of the parallelization by performing a strong and weak scaling analysis.

Speed Up Achievements

Next figure shows the results of the strong scaling analysis from 1 to 48 MareNostrum 4 nodes (48 to 2,304 cores). In this case, we have evaluated 48 mutations, 15K simulation steps per evaluation and mapped one mdrun task to one node (48 MPI processes). mdrun tasks run a Molecular Dynamics simulation using the GROMACS software. The duration of this simulation

⁵ Uniprot - ELIXIR dore data resource. (1993) Pklr - pyruvate kinase pklr - homo sapiens (human) - pklr gene and protein. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/P30613>

grows with the number of simulation steps and is, in its turn, parallelized with MPI. The figure shows that scalability is growing close to the ideal. The code of this experiment is available at https://github.com/bioexcel/biobb_wf_mutations.

Fig. 2.- Strong scaling results for 48 mutations analysis (one node per mdrun and 15K steps analysis using different computing nodes for the mdrun task executions)

The results of the weak-scaling analysis are shown in the next figure, where we have increased the number of computing nodes with the number of mutations. In this case, we have seen that the time is quite similar in all the runs, and the efficiency is higher than 0.9 in all the cases.

Fig. 3. - Weak scaling results with a load of one mutation analysis of 15K steps

We have also performed a performance analysis of a massively parallel execution of the application on 800 nodes of MareNostrum 4 (which involves 38,400 cores) with the Pyruvate Kinase protein. The run consisted of 200 simulations using 4 nodes (192 cores for MPI) per simulation. The total number of tasks executed in this run instance is 7,800. Three main tasks for each mutation dominate the execution: *pyruvateKinase_MN.mdrun_pc* (performs a minimization process), *pyruvateKinase_MN.mdrun_pc_cpt* (implements the equilibration of the data) and *pyruvateKinase_MN.mdrun_pc_all* (executes the final simulation). These three tasks are all parallel invocations (with MPI) of GROMACS executed in 4 nodes. Figure 4 shows a timeline with the task view of this execution, where each colour represents a task type. For this analysis we used the Paraver tool⁶.

⁶ <https://tools.bsc.es/paraver>

Fig. 4. - Paraver timeline view of the tasks of the Pyruvate Kinase workflow

Next figure shows the profile of the number of tasks on execution at each moment of the run, being the top value the 800×48 cores of the allocation. This figure shows that for most of the execution time, the allocation is 100% used.

Fig. 5. - Paraver view showing the number of tasks on execution at each moment

The results of the runs, on up to 38,400 cores of the MareNostrum 4 supercomputer, demonstrate that the workflows can be easily scaled to a larger number of nodes and that the optimal configuration of the execution parameters can be obtained without modifying the user code. A complete analysis of the executions also proves that the execution manager (PyCOMPSs) selected in our approach allocates the resources for the different parts of the application in the proper way with an almost 100% utilization of the pool.

Hardware and Performance portability

The code can be run with GPGPUS-based systems by mapping the GROMACS tasks in GPU nodes. PyCOMPSs supports the execution in heterogeneous systems through its user interface that enables the user to provide constraints on the resources that execute the tasks.

Roadmap summary

The development of this workflow is considered to be finished and is used in production. Experiments with larger infrastructure configuration are considered for the workflows for COVID-19 research presented in another instance of this report template.

References

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.04.14.439795v1>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-019-0177-4>

Experiment

Please refer to the experiment section in pmxCV19.

pmxCV19 (WF)

Report on Application Scalability progress

Name of the code	BioExcel workflows used in the COVID-19 research (pmxCV19)
URL	https://github.com/bioexcel/pmxcv19
Application Domain	Drug design, binding affinities
Supported Key Methods (if applicable) ⁷	MD, free energy
License	Licensed under the Apache License 2.0

pmxCV19 is an automated protocol to evaluate changes on binding affinity between SARS-Cov-2 Spike protein (through its Receptor Binding Domain (RBD)) and Human ACE2 (hACE2) receptor, the main complex responsible for SARS-Cov-2 infection, due to single amino acid variants (complex structure used in the text was obtained from PDB code [6VW1](#)). The method evaluates changes in binding free energy using the PMX algorithm (J. Comput. Chem. 36:348-354 (2015)). It requires a large series of short Molecular Dynamic (MD) simulations, executed using GROMACS (Fig. 1). PyCOMPSs programming framework is used to define the tasks of the workflow and to parallelize the execution. The goal of the implemented workflow is to predict binding free energies of a particular mutation in a shorter time. PyCOMPSs is taking advantage of the independence of the short MDs needed, distributing them along the number of available cores.

⁷ Many simulation codes support a range of different methods and can be seen as a collection of codes and in particular scalability depends significantly on the method selected.

Fig. 1.- Relative binding affinity upon residue mutations GROMACS-PMX workflow schema.

The test case chosen to run corresponds to the analysis of the well-known N501Y (British variant) mutation using a protocol based on 125 x 2 independent simulations (forward and reverse), parallelized by PyCOMPSs. Individual simulations have been run on MareNostrum 4 supercomputer using a single node (48 core) per simulation with MPI intra-node parallelization. The experiments focus on evaluating the scalability of the parallelization by performing a strong scaling analysis.

Fig. 2 shows the PyCOMPSs task graph generated for a small size problem (only 6 simulations) where we can observe that it is not a totally embarrassingly parallel problem, but involves different set of tasks and dependencies. While some of these tasks are sequential and are mapped into a single cpu (i.e. mutate_pc or gentop_pc) others are parallelized with MPI and mapped to a whole node (48 cores), (i.e. mdrun_pc or mdrun_dhdl_pc). While the MPI tasks have been in this case mapped to a single node, in general can be mapped to multiple nodes if the complexity of the use case requires it and this is a feature supported by PyCOMPSs.

Fig. 2.- PyCOMPSs task dependence graph for the pmxCV19 workflow. Nodes represent different instances of the tasks, where the color represents a task type .

Speed Up Achievements

Next figure shows the results of the strong scaling analysis from 1 to 128 MareNostrum 4 nodes (48 to 6,144 cores). Hybrid topologies for the alchemical transformation have been prepared using PMX software. A total of 250 short (10ps) thermodynamic integration MD simulations have been run in each job using GROMACS software. Figure 3 shows the differences in time to solution, going from 10 hours (1 worker node + 1 PyCOMPSs master node) to 7 minutes (127 worker nodes + 1 PyCOMPSs master node).

Fig. 3.- Execution time (in minutes) of the pmxCV19 workflow using from 2 to 128 MareNostrum 4 BSC supercomputer nodes (6144 cores).

The scalability plot in Fig. 4 shows how the workflow performs with different numbers of available nodes in terms of speedup, with the ideal speedup as a reference. The baseline to calculate the speedup is the execution of the workflow with 2 nodes (1 worker node + 1 PyCOMPSs master node).

Fig.4.- Scalability study for the pmxCV19 workflow using up to 128 nodes (6144 cores) in MareNostrum 4 BSC supercomputer. Workflow running 250 short MDs.

The highest difference in speedup using 128 nodes is caused by the number of MD simulations chosen for the experiment (250), which is generating a load imbalance in the final phase of the workflow. To test that, two new runs were submitted with a larger workload, in this case using 1000 short MDs (500 forward + 500 reverse). Results are shown in Fig. 5. While still the speedup is not perfect, it has improved from the previous case, showing that for real production runs with a high number of simulations, it will converge towards almost perfect speedup.

Fig. 5.- Scalability study for the pmxCV19 workflow using up to 128 nodes (6144 cores) in MareNostrum 4 BSC supercomputer. Workflow running 1000 short MDs.

The percentage of CPU used in each of allocated supercomputer nodes is shown in Fig. 6 for the execution using 32 nodes for the 1000 simulations case. As shown in the figure, the allocation is 100% used in most of the execution time, with the exception of the first preparation steps of the workflow (frames ensemble extraction, hybrid topology/structure generation).

Fig. 6.- CPU usage of a 32 nodes job (1,536 cores) in the MareNostrum 4 BSC supercomputer. Each line shows the CPU usage in % of a single MareNostrum node.

Hardware and Performance portability

The code can be run with GPGPU-based systems by mapping the GROMACS tasks in GPU nodes. PyCOMPSs supports the execution in heterogeneous systems through its user interface that enables the user to provide constraints on the resources that execute the tasks.

Besides, the possibility to use the CONDA packaging system and the [CONDA pack](#) functionality with the set of [BioExcel Building Blocks](#) (BioBB) modules and the new PyCOMPSs CONDA package allows an easy deployment of the whole workflow in different HPC centers. This approach has been successfully used to deploy the pmxCV19 workflow in EPCC Cirrus, BSC MareNostrum, HPC2N Kebnekaise, JSC Jusuf and TGCC Joliot-Curie Irene ROME supercomputers.

Roadmap summary

<Status and Roadmap for porting to non-microprocessor architectures (e.g. GPGPUs, FPGAs)>

<Status and Roadmap for porting to EuroHPC pre-exascale system architecture/Lessons learned>

<Scalability Roadmap (outline clear targets for the scalability over the duration of the project/next reporting period and outline the basic approach for achieving increased scalability)>

The workflow is being extensively used to predict the effect of the SARS-CoV-2 variants and human polymorphisms on the SARS-CoV-2-human infectivity, and it is currently used to determine possible zoonotic pathways, studying how the infectious disease has been transmitted between species from animals to humans. The project involves the calculation of many mutations between species (up to 30 mutations depending on the pair of species), and will require extensive usage of HPC supercomputing time. PRACE COVID-19 special allocation time was awarded for the study:

<https://prace-ri.eu/investigating-the-impact-of-mutations-in-sars-cov-2/>

The workflow will be ported to MareNostrum 5 as soon as this machine is available and used in production.

References

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.04.14.439795v1>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-019-0177-4>

Experiment (pyMDSetup + pmxCV19)

We would also like to consider the node performance for homogeneous systems. One node of Fugaku has 3,38Tflop/s on 48 cores, therefore an exascale system based on this architecture would require around 300,000 nodes. Total parallelism is $14,4 \cdot 10^6$.

The answers in this report correspond to the case of the BioBB workflows (PyMDSetup and BioExcel workflows used in the COVID-19 research).

What does an exascale application and data set look like? What requirement does this impose on the system:

1. Can you reasonably partition your application across a system of this size?

More than partitioning the problem, we consider increasing the size of it to fit the available parallelism. The actual problem we are solving with the different BioBB workflows can be easily extended by increasing the number of simulations and its accuracy.

2. Does each node have a large enough parcel of work to do?

The same consideration as above can be given. The actual problem we are solving with the different BioBB workflows can be easily extended by increasing the number of simulations and its accuracy.

3. What sort of underlying memory hierarchy is required to support efficient computation at scale?

- size of memory per node and speed

In principle, there are no special requirements on the type of memory hierarchy. However, one of the current open topics in research in PyCOMPSs is the extension of its runtime to be able to map the objects to different levels of the memory hierarchy depending on different object characteristics (frequency of usage, size, etc). This research is performed in the framework of the PhD thesis of Hatem Elshazly in the EXPERTISE ETN, currently visiting HP (previous CRAY) for a topic related to memory management.

Also, there are no strong constraints on the size of the memory per node and speed. Current executions use a maximum of 10% of the memory of the regular MareNostrum nodes (9.6 GB aprox). Since the problem is not memory bound, we do not see specific memory speed requirements.

4. What interconnect is required?

- Speed and topology

The workflows we are running compose MPI tasks with sequential tasks. The interconnect is critical for the MPI tasks, and not so important for the others. PyCOMPSs runtime, when possible, schedules tasks in the same node to exploit locality, reducing the requirements on the interconnect.

5. Where are the bottlenecks – how will you overcome them?

Being PyCOMPSs a task-based programming model, one of the main performance bottlenecks come from the task management itself: task creation, analysis of dependencies (number of parameters) and scheduling.

One of the recent developments of PyCOMPSs (we expect to make it public in the next release in June) is the ability to support task nesting. The task nesting support is based on a new architecture of the runtime where the runtime is distributed in multiple agents that co-operate with a peer-to-peer network. In the case of running in large HPC systems we are considering the structure where a main agent starts the execution, this main agent creates multiple tasks that instantiate new agents, that at the same time will instantiate new agents. Each of the agents run a COMPSs runtime that can create tasks, analyse their dependencies and schedule them. We are considering right now that the last level agent will be mapped to a node of the system.

Another issue that can penalize the performance of the workflows is when the tasks have many parameters. To alleviate this problem, the strategy followed is based on aggregating the parameters in collections that are analysed as a single parameter. PyCOMPSs supports the collection data type and it is able to find dependencies on elements of collections.

In any case, with the current PyCOMPSs runtime without the nesting mechanism, we have been able to perform efficient production runs with up to 500.000 tasks.

6. Should the system be homogeneous or heterogeneous?
- 7.

From the point of view of the application stack, it can be both homogeneous and heterogeneous. Heterogeneity is optional if you are involving in the workflow simulations that can use the GPU (i.e., GROMACS). Other tasks that may exploit GPUs are pure Python tasks annotated with Numba jit directives or tasks making use of libraries such as CuPy that can exploit GPUs.

8. Should the system be flat or have different local areas for different parts of the application?

Both architectures will match this type of workflows, since the previously described agent infrastructure can be organized in a hierarchical way.

9. How does the application (or system) manage resilience?
 - checkpoint: how often, how big, impact on performance?

The workflows rely on PyCOMPSs runtime to manage resilience. A mechanism to support task failures was added in release 2.5 in June 2019. With this mechanism, the user can configure the workflow execution to continue in the appearance of specific task failures. Also, tasks that depend on a failed task can be configured to be cancelled. Currently we are doing developments to support the failure of a

worker node. Another of the current extensions is a checkpointing mechanism for the whole workflow.

The checkpointing mechanism is being designed to be configurable by the user either with temporal checkpoints or with checkpoints on specific points of the workflow (i.e., a group of tasks have been finished). Large granularity tasks that involve MPI simulations would be also checkpointed. The size of the checkpoint for regular tasks will not be specially large, but will depend on the size of the results of the tasks that will be checkpointed. In the case of MPI tasks, again the size will depend on the memory footprint of the task.

We expected a low impact in performance of the checkpoint since it will be performed asynchronously (in parallel with the execution of the workflow). The impact will be in the usage of resources: more file transfers, more I/O operations.

10. What about the numerical stability of the algorithms at exascale?

If the numerical stability is guaranteed by the simulation codes invoked in the workflows, they should be maintained even when run at exascale level. Even the workflow execution is out of order, the sequential coherence is maintained.

Also, what is your target in terms of exascale capacity needs (use case, grand challenge) and when (2025, 2030, 2040)?

Some large sample workflows that we have planned to run are the following:

- **(2025) Classification of clinically relevant Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) mutations by their impact on the binding affinity of FDA-approved drugs (BioExcel-2 Use Case).** Massive study involving 14,000 calculations of the pmxCV19 workflow. 70 systems (combining 24 mutants and 7 drugs). 200 pmxCV19 workflow calculations for each of the systems (10 equilibrium MD replicas for the WT * 10 equilibrium MD replicas for the mutant * 2 -monomer + complex-). The complete job could be computed using up to 2,688,000 cores, with 192 cores (4 MareNostrum nodes) per free energy calculation, consuming a total amount of 32,000,000 core/hours and producing 1.4PB (100GB x pmxCV19 workflow run).
- **(2030) Dynamic PDB.** Generation of microsecond long trajectories for all suitable structures at the Protein Data Bank. It would involve 200,000 simulations following the pymdsetup protocol. Considering a GPU-based supercomputer and an average system size of 200,000 atoms, the job would be able to use 200,000 nodes for 25 days (GROMACS, 40ns/day) to produce 1 microsecond trajectories, summing up to 120,000,000 gpu/hours. Taking a writing frequency of one snapshot every 50ps, the project will need up to 50PB of data storage.
- **(2040) Dynamic PMut.** Simulation of known single missense mutations (for example, 200 per protein), for 100.000 human proteins (considering known structures or predicted). This will imply around 20 million simulations, also run with the pymdsetup protocol. Numbers in this case would be roughly 2 orders of magnitude higher than the previous study.